

THE MEANING AND HISTORY OF THE CONCEPT OF FINANCIAL CONTROLLING**Urazbaeva Ilmira Konysbaevna***Senior Lecturer at the Department of Finance and Business Analytics,
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This article explores the meaning and history of the concept of financial control. Financial control is an important component of financial management and is aimed at ensuring the efficiency, transparency and reliability of the organization's financial transactions. The article examines the evolution of the concept of financial control, starting from its origins and development in various countries. Also are analyzed the basic principles and methods of financial control, its role in the modern economy and its impact on the stability of the financial system. The study allows us to better understand the essence and significance of financial control in the context of modern financial practice.

Аннотация

Данная статья исследует значение и историю понятия финансового контроля. Финансовый контроль является важной составляющей финансового управления и направлен на обеспечение эффективности, прозрачности и надежности финансовых операций организации. В статье рассматривается эволюция понятия финансового контроля, начиная с его зарождения и развития в различных странах. Также анализируются основные принципы и методы финансового контроля, его роль в современной экономике и влияние на устойчивость финансовой системы. Исследование позволяет лучше понять сущность и значение финансового контроля в контексте современной финансовой практики.

Keywords: financial control, financial management, efficiency, principles, evolution, stability of the financial system.

Ключевые слова: финансовый контроль, финансовое управление, эффективность, принципы, эволюция, устойчивость финансовой системы.

Introduction.

Since its inception, the concept of financial control has evolved along with changes in the business environment. Initially, the main focus was on operational processes aimed at efficient organization of production, internal management system and cost control. Digital transformation led to the modernization of both information interaction mechanisms and business models of joint-stock companies, and the emergence of new markets due to the globalization of the economy required economic entities to introduce flexible financial controlling mechanisms and more flexible management methods in order to quickly respond to the effects of environmental factors. In turn, this determined the priority of further improvement of strategic planning tools as the main condition for effective development of joint-stock companies. Constant technological changes caused by the transition from an industrial economy to a knowledge economy have increased competition and the expansion of data collection, processing and analysis capabilities has led to the emergence of new concepts of financial control based on the rapid updating of information necessary for decision-making.

Theoretical aspect of research.

The traditional paradigm, which includes the analysis of financial statements, processing of collected data and short-term oriented processes, has ceased to meet the needs of joint-stock companies that work in a dynamic environment and require objective information for decision-making. The emergence of digital platforms made it possible to combine various financial controlling tools into a single operational management system. However, the effectiveness of their use in the development and implementation of long-term development strategies, in which the coordination of business processes plays a key role in conditions of high uncertainty, does not always meet the requirements of financial management. This indicates the urgency of the need to modernize corporate financial control tools using modern digital technologies. Thus, financial control was introduced in the enterprise. For the emergence of control, the following conditions should be distinguished:

Picture №1. Conditions for the emergence of control¹

The development of financial control as a branch of the economy depends on the following reasons:

- internationalization and diversification of enterprise activity;
- updating the technologies used in production;
- control and adapt to the complexity of the external environment;
- to eliminate the complexity of communication for making management decisions, to provide this system with competent personnel.

Today, the managers of many foreign enterprises emphasize that after the establishment of control departments in the enterprise, the company's income increases, the use of financial, human and other types of resources becomes more correct and costs are reduced significantly. The financial control service of joint-stock companies faces serious tasks, i.e. it is necessary to provide quick collection and detailed analysis of information on all available costs for managing joint-stock companies. The director of joint-stock companies, the head of the financial controlling department and the heads of production departments should have timely and regular information, and in case of possible deviations, it will have a positive effect on making the right decisions.

The word "controlling" comes from the Latin "contra" (against) and "rotulus" (scroll), which means not writing a report, but checking the actual stock situation. In the 16th century, the English word "Contra-rotularius" became the official title of "comtroller" at the royal court. The emergence of this authorized work was the first attempt to solve problems important for its activity with the help of enterprise management. Later, it appeared in Western Europe and the United States, and is gradually developing in Asian countries. It should be noted here that there is currently no financial

controlling system in developing joint-stock companies. In our country, interest in financial control began in 2000, its introduction is required by the period of unification of real and legal principles of economic activity. In large industrial enterprises, instead of planning and economic departments, financial-economic analysis departments and information-analysis departments, financial controlling services are appearing.

Controlling has been interpreted differently in different periods, for example, in 1990-1997, control was understood as cost accounting, in 1997-2000, it was understood as accounting of enterprise costs and results, in 2000-2005, enterprise budgeting, operational planning and cost management, since 2010, control it is used to provide information for financial management, to make operational financial decisions in the enterprise. It is important to understand the essence of the concept of "financial controlling", to determine the opinions of experts in this group. The word "financial controlling" is defined differently by different scientists. In order to support the financial management system and regulate the processes aimed at achieving the goals of joint-stock companies, they play an important role in the introduction of the control system.

Today, in the financial management system of joint stock companies operating in our country, there are different definitions of the term "financial controlling" and the corresponding conceptual approaches are interpreted in different ways. Economists call the concept of financial control internal control, others recognize control as accounting functions oriented to accounting, and the third group of scientists interprets that it serves to provide the management of joint-stock companies with the necessary information to make financial decisions in every forecast of production and economic activity. We will interpret the opinions of different scientists in the table below.

¹ Prepared by the author.

Table №1.

Analysis of scientific approaches to financial controlling²

Authors	Description
Bogatova A. V. Karpova D. A. Novikova N. V.	Financial controlling is a subsystem of enterprise control aimed at maximizing positive financial indicators using methods, methods and means of managing the financial component of the organization.
Karminsky A.M.	Financial controlling is a system of financial relations and financial flows from reagents in the characteristics of production, logistics, financial, marketing, rationalization, investment and other activities.
Martyushova L.A.	Financial controlling, as a tool for economic analysis, budgeting and crisis management, involves the development of a program capable of timely determining the state of the main indicators of the enterprise at the stage of entry into the crisis zone by enterprise managers.
Soldatov V. V.	Financial control is a tool that allows you to effectively resist the negative effects of the external environment, develop and implement modern management approaches in the company.
Ohanyan M.Sh.	Financial controlling is the management of financial relationships, financial resources and their sources through financial methods, methods, models and tools of financial management.
Shebzukhova M.A.	Financial controlling is a management system in an enterprise that modern companies are actively implementing in order to concentrate control operations on the main aspects of financial activities and to improve overall management efficiency.
Kazakova ³	Financial controlling is effective financial flows that ensure the reliability and timely execution of analytical information about business processes, taking into account the institutional characteristics of holdings in the context of international integration, business diversification, the complexity of economic processes and the methods of implementation of financial and economic activities. aimed at creating a management system.

As we have seen, there are different views on financial controlling, but from the opinions of scientists, it can be concluded that financial management needs quality information to make the right financial decisions. It is important to collect, analyze and organize the obtained data using an internal accounting system that allows monitoring of control indicators.

In our opinion, financial controlling is necessary to support the business of joint-stock companies for making strategic and operational decisions. Deviations from the chosen direction are determined by collecting information about the actual state of the enterprise's activities, and a decision is made to eliminate the deviations in order to achieve the goal. The financial management system covers the entire enterprise and plays

the role of a specific effective indicator of a lot of information about its production and economic activity.

In our opinion, we believe that financial controlling is a separate field of activity in enterprises that is related to the implementation of the economic function and is aimed at making the right strategic and quick decisions by high-ranking employees.

Methodological aspect of research.

Financial controlling also uses methods related to management accounting. Accounting has a special place in the system of finance, personnel and resource control. As a rule, traditional reporting involves focusing on the past and providing factual information about past processes and events, and control reporting focuses on the future.

Picture №2. Tasks of financial control in the financial management system of joint-stock companies⁴

² Prepared by the author.

³ Kazakova N.A. Financial controlling and holding. Monograph. Infra-M. 237 p. of 2016.

⁴ Prepared by the author.

Thus, it can be seen that the establishment of a financial control system in joint-stock companies helps to create a permanent control over the processes to determine the consequences of certain financial management decisions. It can also be said that the introduction of control allows to protect the management of joint-stock companies from making hasty or useless decisions that lead to the expenditure of resources.

It can be seen from the pic.№2 that financial controlling provides the following:

- shareholding control within the company;
- control by commercial banks and other financial and credit organizations;
- independent audit control.

As a result of financial control:

Implementation of strategies of shareholders and investors, effective management of supervisory board and executive bodies;

-implementation of the financial strategy by the executive body, management of current and operational activities, increasing labor productivity;

-investors- are able to determine the stability of the development of enterprises, the potential of their activity and to be aware of them;

- the level of mutual understanding of goals, tasks, actions among employees increases.

Analyze and result of research.

The purpose of financial control is to ensure and improve the effectiveness of the use of financial resources by joint-stock companies, to implement the prepared financial report indicators in accordance with the strategic and tactical plan of the enterprise. These tasks, briefly described, belong to specific subjects and must be performed by the service or department that performs the control function. The role of the planning department in the implementation of these tasks is of particular importance. The development of the planning methodology and its organization include the following: creation of a regulatory and legal framework that will help to implement the forecasts of the development of the joint-stock company; providing advice and assistance to persons developing strategic plans; preparation of various financial and strategic plans, determination of the main goals of joint-stock companies, and execution of coordination work in the preparation of the budget.

Picture №3. The role of financial control in the financial management system of joint-stock companies⁵

Monitoring the implementation of plans aimed at achieving strategic goals for financial controlling tasks; monitoring the state of environmental conditions related to the development of strategic plans; will consist of identifying weaknesses identified during the planning or analysis of program implementation. The task of organizing activities in the monitoring system of financial controlling implies the following:

- development of the internal legal framework for obtaining and providing information within joint-stock companies;
- development of measures providing additional information and analytical support.

Based on this goal, the following main control tasks are distinguished in the management of joint-stock companies: development of planning methodology and its organization; accounting, including data collection and processing; control; organization of activities in the financial monitoring system based on the

plan. In the picture below, we consider the place of financial control in the financial management system of joint-stock companies.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that at different stages of economic development, there is a need to determine the functions of financial controlling and their content. Through financial controlling, the financial decisions and actions of joint-stock companies, the company's assets, income and expenses, the level of profit, cash, various risks, other financial information, i.e. financial transactions, relations with counterparties, investments, financial liquidity of joint-stock companies are always under control and they are regulated. the possibility remains high.

⁵ Prepared by the author.

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